

Privacy-Preserving Online Content Moderation with Federated Learning

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Motivation

Online Social Networks users daily consume a high volume of online information. Often online information may express **hatefulness, cyberbullying, toxicity, aggressiveness, racism**, or other harmful behaviors.

“Online Content Moderation Tools for users’ protection”

Platforms use **Machine Learning (ML)** techniques to build **automated tools** to detect harmful online content.

ML requires central **processing of user data**, which raises concerns regarding **compliance with privacy policies** (i.e., **GDPR**).

In [1], we propose a **Differentially Private Federated Learning framework** to build privacy-preserving online content moderation tools with the following **objectives**:

- adequate model’s performance
- preserve user privacy
- low overhead on user’s machine

Differentially Private Federated Learning

Federated Learning (FL): A central aggregator (server) coordinates the training. The clients (users) train the ML model on their device with locally stored data and send the model’s updates to the server. The server collects the updates, aggregates them, and applies the aggregated update to the global model. In the FL approach, the **user does not share raw data** with a central entity but **only shares the model’s updates**. With FL, privacy leaks can still occur. One threat is **membership inference attacks**.

Differential Privacy (DP) provides privacy guarantees (at the user level) against membership inference attacks by an external attacker. We assume that the attacker has access to the trained model and tries to perform unwanted inferences of the data belonging to the users who participated in the training process. When applying DP to the FL solution, the server **adds noise to the sum of the updates** received from the individual clients before their aggregation.

- adequate classifier’s performance with a **medium user-level privacy**, even with: a **few clients** per round, a **few data** per client
- FL trained classifier** approaches the performance of the classifier trained with traditional ML (centralized)
- the non-private **FL trained classifier** can **generalize** to capture **different types of user misbehavior** and obtain a **promising performance**
- the local training **does not introduce excessive CPU utilization and memory consumption overhead** to the user device

Evaluation

We **simulate a text classifier — in an FL fashion — which can detect tweets with harmful content**. We **simulate the users’ browsing history** by splitting a centralized Twitter dataset into a number of disjoint sets to construct artificial clients. We evaluate the classifier with five Twitter datasets (labeled with different types of misbehavior): (1) **Abusive**, (2) **Sarcastic**, (3) **Hateful**, (4) **Offensive**, and (5) **Cyberbullying**.

private-FL vs non-private-FL:

Fig. A: 628 total clients - each client has 100 data points (balanced), client sampling per FL round.

Fig. B: varying the number of clients, data per client, and classes ratio.

Conclusion

We can build ML models to detect harmful content with promising performance using the DP-FL approach. Platforms can follow this approach to develop online content moderation tools while preserving their users’ privacy.

References

- [1] Leonidou, P.; et al. Privacy-Preserving Online Content Moderation with Federated Learning. Companion Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3543873.3587366>

